

The antifungal spectrum of medicinal plants: A review

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Abstract

Medicinal plant possessed antifungal effects by many mechanisms, they caused membrane disturbance resulting in the loss of membrane integrity, inhibited DNA transcription and reduced the cell populations, inhibited the activity of fungal antioxidant enzymes and inhibited fungal biofilm formation. The current review discussed the antifungal effects of medicinal plants.

Keywords: Medicinal plant; Pharmacology; Antifungal; Natural; Therapeutics

1. Introduction

Traditional medicine is based on beliefs and practices that existed before the development of so-called modern medicine or scientific drug therapy. However, the recent pharmacological studies showed that the medicinal plants exerted many pharmacological effects, among these, the antifungal properties against dermatophytes and yeasts as a single treatment or combined with other antifungal agents, and some clinical trials showed that medicinal plants can be applied as an alternative antifungal agents for fungal diseases caused by traditional drugs- resistant fungal species [1-5]. Medicinal plant possessed antifungal effects by many mechanisms, they caused membrane disturbance resulting in the loss of membrane integrity, inhibited DNA transcription and reduced the cell populations, inhibited the activity of fungal antioxidant enzymes and inhibited fungal biofilm formation [6-16]. The current review will highlight the antifungal effects of medicinal plants.

Table 1 Medicinal plants with antifungal effects

Medicinal plants	Active components	Antifungal spectrum	Ref.
<i>Adiantum capillus-veneris</i>	extracted phenols	<i>Aspergillus niger</i> and <i>Rhizopus stolonifer</i>	17-18
<i>Alhagi graecorum</i>	methanol extract	<i>Aspergillus flavus</i> , <i>Alternaria alternate</i> , <i>Fusarium oxysporum</i> , <i>Fusarium solani</i> , <i>Bipolaris oryzae</i> , <i>Chetomium</i> and <i>Mucor</i>	19-20
<i>Allium sativum</i>	aqueous extract	<i>Cryptococcus neoformans</i> , <i>Candida</i> , <i>Cryptococcus</i> , <i>Trichophyton</i> , <i>Epidermophyton</i> , and <i>Microsporium</i> species	21-26
<i>Alpinia galangal</i>	essential oil from fresh rhizomes	<i>Trichophyton mentagrophytes</i> , <i>Trichophyton mentagrophytes</i> , <i>Trichophyton rubrum</i> , <i>Trichophyton concentricum</i> , <i>Rhizopus stolonifer</i> ,	27-33

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		<i>Aspergillus niger</i> , <i>Colletotrichum musae</i> and <i>Fusarium oxysporum</i>	
<i>Ammi majus</i>	acetone and 95% ethanol extract	<i>Neurospora crassa</i>	34-35
<i>Anchusa strigosa</i>	aqueous extract	<i>Microsporum canis</i> , <i>Trichophyton mentagrophytes</i> and <i>Trichophyton violaceum</i>	36-37
<i>Apium graveolens</i>	methanolic extract	<i>Trichophyton longifuss</i> , <i>Candida albicans</i> , <i>Aspergillus flavus</i> , <i>Microsporum canis</i> , <i>Fusarium solani</i> and <i>Candida glabrata</i>	38-39
<i>Arachis hypogaea</i>	stilbenoids	Genera: <i>Colletotrichum</i> , <i>Botrytis</i> , <i>Fusarium</i> , and <i>Phomopsis</i>	40-43
<i>Arundo donax</i>	crude extracts	<i>Trametes versicolor</i> , <i>Coniophora puteana</i> , <i>Gloeophyllum trabeum</i> and <i>Postia placenta</i>	44-45
<i>Asclepias curassavica</i>	crude methanolic extract	<i>Helminthosporium oryzae</i> , <i>Aspergillus niger</i> and <i>Fusarium oxysporum</i>	46-49
<i>Asparagus officinalis</i>	saponin	<i>Candida</i> , <i>Cryptococcus</i> , <i>Trichophyton</i> , <i>Microsporum</i> and <i>Epidermophyton</i> Species	50-52
<i>Asphodelus fistulosus</i>	aqueous extract	<i>Trichophyton violaceum</i>	53
<i>Avena sativa</i>	protein fraction	<i>Penicillium roqueforti</i>	54-55
<i>Ballota nigra</i>	essential oils	<i>Fusarium</i> , <i>Botrytis cinerea</i> , and <i>Alternaria solani</i>	56-58
<i>Bellis perennis</i>	triterpenoid glycosides	<i>Candida</i> and <i>Cryptococcus</i> species	59-60
<i>Benincasa hispida</i>	methanolic extract	<i>Candida albicans</i> and <i>Aspergillus niger</i>	61-62
<i>Betula alba</i>	betulinic acid	<i>Candida albicans</i>	63-64
<i>Bidens tripartitus</i>			
<i>Brassica nigra</i>			
<i>Brassica rapa</i>	peptide, crude extracts and fractions	<i>Candida albicans</i> , <i>Fusarium oxysporum</i> and <i>Mycosphaerella arachidicola</i>	65-69
<i>Caesalpinia crista</i>	α -(2-hydroxy-2-methylpropyl)- ω -(2-hydroxy-3-methylbut-2-en-1-yl) polymethylene, isolated from ethyl acetate leaf extract	<i>Candida albicans</i> and <i>Rhodotorula</i> Species	70-71
<i>Calamintha graveolens</i>	essential oil	<i>Candida albicans</i>	72
<i>Calendula officinalis</i>	methanol and ethanol extracts	<i>Candida albicans</i> , <i>Candida dubliniensis</i> and <i>Candida parapsilosis</i>	73-77
<i>Calotropa procera</i>	crude flavonoid, chloroform, methanol and ethyl acetate extracts	<i>Trichophyton rubrum</i> , <i>Trichophyton tonsurans</i> , <i>Trichophyton mentagrophyte</i> , <i>Epidermophyton floccosum</i> , <i>Aspergillus</i> Sp. and <i>Fusarium solani</i>	78-81
<i>Capparis spinosa</i>	ethanolic extract	<i>Alternaria alternata</i> , <i>Fusarium oxysporum</i> , <i>Phoma destructiva</i> , <i>Rhizoctonia solani</i> , and <i>Sclerotium rolfsii</i>	83-84

<i>Capsella bursa-pastoris</i>	shepherin I and II peptides	<i>Candida</i> species	85-86
<i>Capsicum annum</i>	extracts	<i>Aspergillus niger</i> and <i>Candida albicans</i>	87-88
<i>Carum Carvi</i>	essential oil	<i>Fusarium sulphureum</i> , <i>Phoma exigua</i> var. <i>foveata</i> , <i>Helminthosporium solani</i> , <i>Cladosporium cladosporioides</i> , <i>Fulvia fulvum</i> , <i>Alternaria alternata</i> , <i>Phoma macdonaldii</i> and <i>Phomopsis helianthi</i>	89-90
<i>Cassia occidentalis</i>	crude extracts	<i>Candida albicans</i> , <i>Aspergillus clavatus</i> and <i>Aspergillus niger</i>	91-92
<i>Chenopodium album</i>	methanol and n-hexane extracts	<i>Macrophomina phaseolina</i> and <i>Candida albicans</i>	93-95
<i>Chrozophora tinctoria</i>	crude methanol extract	<i>Fusarium moniliformes</i> , <i>Fusarium oxysporum</i> , <i>Fusarium solani</i> , <i>Aspergillus niger</i> , <i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i> , <i>Aspergillus flavus</i> , <i>Alternaria</i> sp., <i>Mucor</i> sp., <i>Rhizoctonia solani</i> , and <i>Cochliobolus sativus</i>	96-98
<i>Chrysanthemum cinerariaefolium</i>	methanolic and ethanolic leaf extract	<i>Candida tropicalis</i> , <i>Candida albicans</i> , <i>Candida albicans</i> , <i>Candida parapsilosis</i> and <i>Candida cruzei</i>	99
<i>Cicer arietinum</i>	several peptides	<i>Candida krusei</i> , <i>Candida tropicalis</i> , <i>Candida parapsilosis</i> , <i>Mycosphaerella arachidicola</i> , <i>Botrytis cinerea</i> , <i>Fusarium oxysporum</i> and <i>Drechslera tetramera</i>	100-104
<i>Cichorium intybus</i>	seeds extract/ fractions guaianolides-rich root extracts	<i>Aspergillus flavus</i> and <i>A. niger</i> , <i>R. solani</i> and <i>Sachharomyces cerevisiae</i> . <i>Trichophyton tonsurans</i> , <i>T. rubrum</i> , and <i>T. Violaceum</i>	105-108
<i>Cistanche tubulosa</i>	crude extract, phenylethanoid glycosides, campneosid I and II	<i>Aspergillus niger</i> and <i>Aspergillus fumigates</i>	109
<i>Citrullus colocynthis</i>	aqueous and diluted acetone extracts	<i>Candida glabrata</i> , <i>Candida albicans</i> , <i>Candida parapsilosis</i> , <i>Candida kreusei</i> , <i>Aspergillus ochraceus</i> and <i>Aspergillus flavus</i>	110-112
<i>Citrus</i> (<i>C aurantifolia</i> , <i>C limonum</i> , <i>C medica</i> , <i>C medica</i> var <i>limetta</i> , <i>C sinensis</i>)	juice of the fruit, burnt rind of the fruit and oil	<i>Aspergillus niger</i> , <i>Aspergillus flavus</i> , <i>Aspergillus fumigates</i> , <i>Candida albicans</i> , <i>Mucor</i> Sp and <i>Pencillium</i> Sp.	113-122
<i>Clerodendrom inerme</i> (<i>Volkameria inermis</i>)	ethanol, benzene and aqueous extracts	<i>Aspergillus niger</i> , <i>Aspergillus flavus</i> , <i>Candida albicans</i> , <i>Candida glabrata</i> , <i>Epidermophyton floccosum</i> , <i>Trichophyton mentagrophytes</i> , <i>Trichophyton rubrum</i> , <i>Trichophyton tonsurans</i> , <i>Aspergillus niger</i> , <i>Aspergillus flavus</i> , <i>Curvularia lunata</i> , <i>Botrytis cinerea</i> and <i>Fusarium oxysporum</i>	123-125
<i>Clitoria ternatea</i>	crude extract and protein	<i>Cryptococcus neoformans</i> , <i>Cryptococcus albidus</i> , <i>Cryptococcus laurentii</i> , <i>Candida albicans</i> , <i>Candida parapsilosis</i> , <i>Curvularia</i> sp., <i>Alternaria</i> sp., <i>Cladosporium</i> sp., <i>Aspergillus flavus</i> , <i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i> , <i>Aspergillus niger</i> , <i>Rhizopus</i> sp., <i>Sclerotium</i> sp, <i>Rhizoctonia solani</i> , <i>Fusarium solani</i> , <i>Colletotrichum lindemuthianum</i> , <i>Lasiodiplodia</i>	126-131

		<i>theobromae</i> , <i>Pyricularia grisea</i> , <i>Bipolaris oryzae</i> and <i>Colletotrichum gloeosporioides</i>	
<i>Corchorus acutangulus</i> (<i>Corchorus aestuans</i>)	various solvent extracts	<i>Aspergillus niger</i> , <i>Candida albicans</i> , <i>Candida tropicalis</i> , <i>Candida kefyr</i> , <i>Cryptococcus neoformans</i> , <i>Rhizopus stolonifer</i> and <i>Saccharomyces cerevisiae</i>	132-133
<i>Corchorus capsularis</i>	crude methanolic extract	<i>Candida albicans</i> and <i>Saccharomyces cerevisiae</i>	134-135
<i>Coriandrum sativum</i>	essential oils	<i>Aspergillus niger</i> , <i>Candida albicans</i> , <i>Candida kefyr</i> , <i>Candida tropicalis</i> , <i>Microsporium canis</i> ,	136-144
<i>Cressa cretica</i>	hexane, ethyl acetate and methanol extracts	<i>Candida albicans</i> , <i>Candida tropicalis</i> , <i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i> , <i>Aspergillus flavus</i> , <i>Aspergillus niger</i> , <i>Fusarium oxysporum</i> , <i>Penicillium citrinum</i> , <i>Paecilomyces varioti</i> , <i>Microsporium gypseum</i> and <i>Trichophyton rubrum</i>	145-149
<i>Crotalaria juncea</i>	aqueous extract	<i>Aspergillus flavus</i> , <i>A. niger</i> , <i>Fusarium solani</i> , <i>Macrophomina phaseolina</i> and <i>Rhizoctonia solani</i>	150-151
<i>Cuminum cyminum</i>	essential oil	<i>Trichophyton rubrum</i> , <i>Candida albicans</i> , <i>Aspergillus niger</i> , <i>Aspergillus flavus</i> , <i>Saccharomyces cerevisiae</i> and <i>Candida albicans</i> , <i>R. stolonifer</i> , <i>Verticillium dahliae</i> , <i>Rhizoctonia cerealis</i> , <i>Alternaria alternata</i> , <i>Alternaria solani</i> , <i>Gaeumannomyces graminis</i> , <i>Sclerotinia sclerotiorum</i> , <i>Phytophthora capsici</i> , <i>Thanatephorus cucumeris</i> , <i>Blumeria graminis</i> , and <i>Botrytis cinerea</i>	152-166
<i>Cupressus sempervirens</i>	chloroform extracts and essential oil	<i>Candida albicans</i> , <i>C. terus</i> , <i>Trichoderma reesei</i> , <i>Saccharomyces cerevisiae</i> , <i>Aspergillus niger</i> , <i>Aspergillus flavus</i> , <i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i> , <i>Fusarium solani</i> , <i>Fusarium oxysporium</i> , <i>Fusarium culmorum</i> , <i>Fusarium equiseti</i> , <i>Fusarium verticillioides</i> , <i>Fusarium nygamai</i> , <i>P. digitatum</i> , <i>Botrytis cinerea</i> , <i>Microdochium nivale</i> var. <i>nivale</i> and <i>Alternaria</i> sp	167-173
<i>Cydonia oblonga</i>	ethanolic and acetonetic extracts	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	174-175
<i>Cymbopogon schoenanthus</i>	aqueous and organic extracts	<i>A. flavus</i> , <i>A. niger</i> , <i>C. spicifer</i> , <i>F. dimerum</i> , <i>M. circinelloides</i> , <i>Alternaria alternata</i> , <i>Cochliobolous spicifer</i> , <i>Stachybotrys atra</i> var <i>microspora</i> , and <i>Ulocladium botrytis</i> , <i>Candida albicans</i> , <i>Candida tropicalis</i> , <i>Candida krusei</i> , <i>Epidermophyton floccosum</i> , <i>Trichophyton rubrum</i> , <i>Trichophyton mentagrophytes</i> , <i>Trichophyton verrucosum</i> and <i>Microsporium canis</i>	176-178
<i>Cynodon dactylon</i>	ethanol, methanol, acetone, chloroform, hexane and petroleum ether extract	<i>Aspergillus niger</i> , <i>Candida albicans</i> , <i>Candida kefyr</i> and <i>Candida tropicalis</i>	178-179
<i>Cyperus rotundus</i>	essential oil	<i>Candida parapsilosis</i> , <i>Aspergillus flavus</i> , <i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i> and <i>Fusarium oxysporum</i>	180-182
<i>Dactyloctenium aegyptiacum</i>	ethyl acetate, <i>n</i> -butanol and ethanolic extracts	<i>Aspergillus fumigates</i> , <i>Aspergillus niger</i> and <i>Candida albicans</i>	183-184

<i>Datisca cannabina</i>	crude extracts	<i>Candida albicans</i> and <i>Aspergillus niger</i>	185
<i>Datura fastuosa</i>	hexane, chloroform, acetone, methanolic fractions and 2beta-(3,4-dimethyl-2,5-dihydro-1H-pyrrol-2-yl)-1'-methylethyl pentanoate isolated from the leaves	<i>A. fumigatus</i> , <i>A. flavus</i> and <i>A. niger</i> .	186-188
<i>Datura stramonium</i>	chloroform and ethanol extracts of branches and leaves	<i>Candida albicans</i> , <i>Candida utilis</i> , <i>Saccharomyces cerevisiae</i> , <i>Aspergillus fumigates</i> , <i>Aspergillus niger</i> , <i>Aspergillus parasiticus</i> , <i>Fusarium semitectum</i> , <i>Fusarium colmorum</i> , <i>Fusarium oxysporum</i> , <i>Ceratocystis ulmi</i> and <i>Rhizoctonia solani</i> , <i>Colletotrichum gloeosporioides</i> , <i>Trichoderma harzianum</i> , <i>Phytophthora nicotiana</i> , <i>Pythium ultimum</i> and <i>Rhizoctonia solani</i>	189-198
<i>Desmostachya bipinnata</i>	Ethanol extract	<i>Candida tropicalis</i> , <i>Candida albicans</i> , <i>Aspergillus fumigates</i> , <i>Aspergillus flavus</i> and <i>Penicillium chrysogenum</i>	199-200
<i>Dianthus caryophyllus</i>	two benzoic acid derivatives, protocatechuic acid (3,4-dihydroxybenzoic acid) and vanillic acid (4-hydroxy-3-methoxy benzoic acid)	<i>Fusarium oxysporum</i>	201-202
<i>Dodonaea viscosa</i>	aqueous, methanol, chloroform and acetone extracts	<i>Candida albicans</i> , <i>Curvularia lunata</i> , <i>Fusarium oxysporum</i> , <i>Penicillium citrinum</i> , <i>Aspergillus niger</i> , <i>Aspergillus flavus</i> , <i>Paecilomyces varioti</i> , <i>Microsporium gypseum</i> , and <i>Trichophyton rubrum</i>	203-208
<i>Dolichos lablab</i> (syn: <i>Lablab purpureus</i>)	chloroform, n-hexane, ethyl acetate extracts	<i>Saccharomyces cereviceae</i> , <i>Candida albicans</i> , <i>Aspergillus niger</i> , <i>Fusarium oxysporum</i> , <i>Rhizoctonia solani</i> , <i>Coprinus comatus</i>	209-212
<i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i>	peptide EcAMP1	<i>F. graminearum</i> , <i>F. solani</i> , <i>A. alternata</i> , <i>A. solani</i> , <i>B. sorokiniana</i> , <i>P. infestans</i> , <i>P. debaryanum</i> , and <i>P. Ultimum</i>	213-214
<i>Echium italicum</i>	oil	<i>Aspergillus niger</i> and <i>Candida albicans</i>	215-216
<i>Ephedra alata</i> and <i>Ephedra foliata</i>	different crude extracts	<i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i> , <i>Penicillium italicum</i> , <i>Syncephalastrum racemosum</i> , and <i>Candida albicans</i>	217-219
<i>Equisetum arvense</i>	oil	<i>Aspergillus niger</i> and <i>Candida albicans</i>	220-221
<i>Erigeron Canadensis</i> (Syn: <i>Conyza canadensis</i>)	essential oil, ethanol and methanol extracts	<i>T. longifusus</i> , <i>M. canis</i> , <i>Candida albicans</i> , <i>Candida glabrata</i> , <i>Candida parapsilosis</i> , <i>Candida tropicalis</i> , <i>C. lindemuthianum</i> , <i>Cryptococcus neoformans</i> , <i>A. flavus</i> , <i>F. solani</i> and <i>C. glaberata</i>	222-228
<i>Erodium cicutarium</i>	essential oils	<i>A. restrictus</i> , <i>A. chrysogenum</i> , <i>A. fumigatus</i> and <i>C. Albicans</i>	227-228
<i>Eryngium creticum</i>	aqueous extracts	<i>M. canis</i> , <i>T. mentagrophytes</i> and <i>T. violaceum</i>	229-230

<i>Eucalyptus</i> Species	essential oil, methanolic and aqueous leaf extracts	<i>Aspergillus niger</i> , <i>Candida albicans</i> , <i>Penicillium digitatum</i> , <i>Microsporum canis</i> , <i>Microsporum gypseum</i> , <i>Trichophyton rubrum</i> , <i>Trichophyton schoenleinii</i> , <i>Trichophyton mentagrophytes</i> and <i>Epedermophyton floccosum</i>	231-236
<i>Eupatorium cannabinum</i>	essential oil, chloroformic, water and hydroalcoholic extract	<i>Candida albicans</i> , <i>Aspergillus niger</i> , <i>Trichoderma lignorum</i> and <i>Fusarium oxysporum</i>	237-239
<i>Euphorbia hirta</i> (syn: <i>Euphorbia pilulifera</i>)	acetone, chloroform, ethyl acetate, benzene, butanol, ethanol, dimethyl formamide and diethyl ether extracts	<i>Candida albicans</i> , <i>T. mentagrophytes</i> , <i>Aspergillus niger</i> , <i>Aspergillus flavus</i> , <i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i> , <i>Aspergillus erythrocephalus</i> and <i>Fusarium</i> spp.	240-244
<i>Euphorbia tinctoria</i> (syn: <i>Euphorbia macroclada</i>)	methanol extracts of the flowering branches	<i>Candida albicans</i> , <i>Candida tropicalis</i> , <i>Candida glabrata</i> , <i>Candida parapsilosis</i> , <i>Candida krusei</i> , <i>Trichophyton</i> sp., <i>Epidermophyton</i> sp., <i>Verticillium dahliae</i> , <i>Fusarium oxysporum</i> , <i>Rhizopus stolonifer</i> , <i>Penicillium italicum</i> , <i>Rhizoctonia solani</i> , <i>Alternaria solani</i> , <i>Stemphylium solani</i> , <i>Cladosporium</i> sp., <i>Mucor</i> sp., and <i>Pythium</i> sp.	245-247
<i>Fagopyrum esculentum</i>	peptides	<i>Fusarium oxysporum</i> and <i>Mycosphaerella arachidicola</i>	248-249
<i>Ficus carica</i>	methanolic, ethyl acetate, hexan and chloroformic extracts	<i>Candida albicans</i> , <i>Cryptococcus neoformans</i> and <i>Microsporum canis</i>	250-252
<i>Ficus religiosa</i>	oil and aqueous extract of bark leaf, stem and fruit	<i>Aspergillus niger</i> and <i>Candida albicans</i>	253-255
<i>Foeniculum vulgare</i>	essential oil, organic and aqueous leaves extracts	<i>Aspergillus niger</i> , <i>Aspergillus flavus</i> , <i>Fusarium graminearum</i> , <i>Candida albicans</i> and <i>Rhizopus stolonifer</i>	256-260
<i>Fraxinus ornus</i>	<i>n</i> -hexane fraction of seeds	<i>Candida albicans</i>	261
<i>Fumaria officinalis</i>	N-octacosan 7 β ol isolated from the methanol extract	<i>Candida albicans</i> and <i>Aspergillus niger</i>	262-263
<i>Galium aparine</i>	lipophilic complex	<i>Candida albicans</i>	264-266
<i>Galium verum</i>	water, alcohol (70%) and chloroform extracts	<i>Candida albicans</i>	267
<i>Glossostemon bruguieri</i>	ethanolic extract	<i>Aspergillus flavus</i> , <i>Aspergillus fumigates</i> and <i>Penicillium chrysogenum</i>	268
<i>Glycyrrhiza glabra</i>	extracts of rhizomes and roots	<i>Candida albicans</i> , <i>C. glabrata</i> , <i>C. parapsilosis</i> , <i>C. tropicalis</i> <i>Aspergillus niger</i> , <i>Aspergillus flavus</i> , <i>Aspergillus awamorii</i> and <i>Rhizopus solani</i>	269-271
<i>Gnaphalium luteoalbum</i>	acetone leaf extract	<i>Aspergillus parasiticus</i> , <i>Aspergillus niger</i> , <i>Colletotrichum gloeosporioides</i> , <i>Fusarium oxysporum</i> , <i>Penicillium expansum</i> , <i>Penicillium janthinellum</i> , <i>Phytophthora nicotiana</i> , <i>Pythium ultimum</i> and <i>Trichoderma harzianum</i>	272

<i>Gossypium Species</i>	basic proteins and oils	<i>Trichophyton rubrum, Candida albicans, Botrytis cinerea, Alternaria brassicicola, Chalara elegans</i> and <i>Fusarium oxysporum</i>	274-275
<i>Haplophyllum species</i>	ethanolic, polyphenolic and alkaloid extracts	<i>Aspergillus fumigates, Aspergillus flavus, Aspergillus parasiticus, Geotricum candidum</i> and <i>Syncephalastrum racemosum, Aspergillus parasiticus</i> and <i>Mucor</i> sp	276-278
<i>Hedera helix</i>	α -hederin	<i>Candida</i> sp	279-281
<i>Helianthus tuberosus</i>	The leaf extracts and phenolic acids	<i>Botrytis cinerea, Colletotrichum gloeosporioides, Phytophthora capsici, Alternaria solani, Rhizoctonia cerealis</i> and <i>Rhizoctonia solani</i>	282-284
<i>Helicophyllum Species</i>	The ethanolic leave extracts	<i>C. tropicalis, C. albicans, C. dublicans,</i> and <i>C. krusei</i>	285-286
<i>Heliotropium Species</i>	<i>n</i> -hexane, butanol, aqueous, ethyl acetate methanol and chloroform leaves, flowers, and stem extracts	<i>Aspergillus niger, Aspergillus flavus, Aspergillus parasiticus, Aspergillus oryzae, Aspergillus fumigates, Trichoderma longibrachiantum, Fusarium solani</i> and <i>Candida albicans</i>	287-288
<i>Hibiscus rosa-sinensis</i>	methanol, chloroform, <i>n</i> -hexane and aqueous extracts	<i>Candida parapsilosis, Candida glabrata, Candida albicans</i> and <i>Aspergillus niger, Aspergillus flavus</i> and <i>Trichophyton rubrum</i>	289-291
<i>Hibiscus sabdariffa</i>	methanolic leaves extracts	<i>Candida albicans, Aspergillus niger</i>	292-295
<i>Hyoscyamus Species</i>	methanolic extracts of the seeds	<i>Candida albicans, Candida tropicalis, Candida guilliermondii, Candida krusei, Candida glabrata, Candida lusitaniae, Candida kefyri, Candida parapsilosis, Cryptococcus neoformans, Aspergillus fumigatus, Aspergillus flavus, Scopulariopsis brevicaulis, Cryptococcus laurentii, Trichophyton mentagrophytes, Trichophyton rubrum, Trichophyton soudanense, Microsporum canis, Microsporum gypseum, Epidermophyton floccosum</i>	296-298
<i>Hypericum triquetrifolium</i>	essential oils	<i>Aspergillus niger, Fusarium solani, Botrytis cinerea, Candida albicans, Candida glabrata</i> and <i>Candida krusei</i>	299-301
<i>Inula graveolens</i> (<i>Syn: Dittrichia graveolens</i>)	Volatile oil	<i>Candida albicans</i>	302-303
<i>Iris pallid</i>	Iridal, a triterpenoidic compound	<i>Candida albicans</i> and <i>Candida parapsilosis</i>	304
<i>Jasminum officinale</i>	different solvent extracts of the flowers and whole plant (leaves, barks and roots)	<i>Candida albicans</i> and <i>Aspergillus niger</i>	306-307
<i>Jasminum sambac</i>	methanol extract and essential oil	<i>Malassezia</i> sp and <i>Alternaria</i> sp	308-310
<i>Juglans regia</i>	methanolic, ethyl acetate, alkaloid, and hydrolyzed	<i>Ascosphaera apis</i> and <i>Candida albicans</i>	311-313

	methanolic extract of the leaves		
<i>Juniperus communis</i>	many fractions as well as essential oil	<i>Candida albicans</i> , <i>Alternaria</i> sp, <i>Aspergillus nidulans</i> , and <i>Aspergillus niger</i>	314-315
<i>Juniperus oxycedrus</i>	methanolic extract of the leaves and oil	<i>Alternaria tenuis</i> , <i>Aspergillus niger</i> , <i>Fusarium oxysporum</i> , <i>Penicillium coryophilum</i> , <i>Trichophyton rubrum</i> and <i>Candida albicans</i>	316-319
<i>Lagerstroemia indica</i>	petroleum ether, chloroform, methanol and distilled water extracts of the barks, leaves and fruits	<i>Candida albicans</i> , <i>A. oryzae</i> and <i>A. niger</i>	320-321
<i>Lagerstroemia speciosa</i>	various extracts of the fruits	<i>Aspergillus niger</i> , <i>Aspergillus flavus</i> and <i>Candida albicans</i>	322
<i>Lallemantia royaleana</i>	methanolic seed extract and essential oil	<i>Aspergillus flavus</i> , <i>Aspergillus niger</i> , <i>Aspergillus parasiticus</i> , <i>Candida albicans</i> and <i>Saccharomyces cerevisiae</i>	323-324
<i>Lantana camara</i>	petroleum ether, acetone, methanolic and water extracts	<i>Trichophyton mentagrophytes</i> , <i>Candida albicans</i> , <i>Candida tropicalis</i> , <i>Saccharomyces cerevisiae</i> , <i>Aspergillus niger</i> , <i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i> , <i>Aspergillus flavus</i> , <i>Penicillium</i> spp., <i>Fusarium oxysporum</i> , <i>Alternaria alternata</i> , <i>Sclerotium rolfsii</i> and <i>Curvularia lunata</i>	325-329
<i>Lawsonia inermis</i>	lawsone and methanol, ethanol, chloroform, ethyl acetate and aqueous leaf and bark extract	<i>Aspergillus niger</i> , <i>Aspergillus flavus</i> , and <i>Penicillium notatum</i> and <i>Fusarium</i> sp, <i>Epidermophyton floccosum</i> , <i>Microsporium audouinii</i> , <i>Microsporium gypseum</i> , <i>Microsporium fulvum</i> , <i>Trichophyton rubrum</i> , <i>Trichophyton concentricum</i> , <i>Trichophyton tonsurans</i> , <i>Trichophyton violaceum</i> , <i>Candida albicans</i> , <i>C. glabrata</i>	330-342
<i>Lemna minor</i>	lyophilized water extract and ethanol extract	<i>Candida parapsilosis</i> and <i>Candida glabrata</i>	343
<i>Lepidium sativum</i>	methanolic, ethanolic and petroleum ether seed extracts	<i>Aspergillus niger</i> , <i>Aspergillus terreus</i> , <i>Aspergillus flavus</i> , <i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i> , <i>Candida albicans</i> , <i>Saccharomyces cerevisiae</i> , <i>Fusarium equiseti</i> , <i>Microsporium canis</i> , <i>Streptococcus faecalis</i> , <i>Mucor</i> sp., <i>Alternaria alternate</i> , <i>Trichoderma viride</i> , <i>Trichoderma horzianum</i> and <i>Trichophyton mentagrophytes</i> , and <i>Penicillium</i> sp	344-349
<i>Linum usitatissimum</i>	seeds extracts	<i>Candida albicans</i>	350
<i>Lippia nodiflora</i>	stem and leaves extracts	<i>Candida albicans</i> , <i>Candida krussii</i> , <i>Candida tropicalis</i> , <i>Aspergillus niger</i> , <i>Trichophyton mentagrophytes</i> , <i>Microsporium gypseum</i> , <i>Malassezia pachydermatis</i> and <i>Cryptococcus neoformans</i>	351-357
<i>Lithospermum officinale</i>	Shikonin	<i>Saccharomyces cerevisiae</i> , <i>Trichophyton rubrum</i> , <i>T. mentagrophytes</i> , <i>T. tonsulans</i> var. <i>sulfureum</i> , <i>Microsporium gypseum</i> , <i>Epidermophyton floccosum</i> , <i>Candida albicans</i> , <i>Candida krusei</i> and <i>C. glabrata</i>	358-359

<i>Luffa acutangula</i>	fruits, leaves, roots and seeds extracts	<i>Candida albicans</i> , <i>Candida tropicalis</i> , <i>Curvularia lunata</i> , <i>Drechslera hawaiiensis</i> , <i>Fusarium equiseti</i> and <i>Phoma sorghina</i>	360-364
<i>Luffa cylindrica</i>	seeds and fruits extracts	<i>Candida albicans</i> , <i>Aspergillus flavus</i> , <i>Aspergillus niger</i> , <i>Aspergillus fumigates</i> , <i>Aspergillus rhizobus</i> , <i>Sacharomyces cerevisiae</i>	365-372
<i>Lycopus europaeus</i>	euroabienol and essential oils	<i>P. chrysogenum</i> , <i>A. restrictus</i> , <i>A. chrysogenum</i> , <i>A. fumigates</i> , <i>C. albicans</i> and <i>S. cerevisiae</i>	372-373
<i>Lythrum salicaria</i>	crude extracts	<i>Candida albicans</i>	374-377
<i>Mangifera indica</i>	peel and seed extracts, flavonoides	<i>Candida</i> , <i>Dekkera</i> , <i>Hanseniaspora</i> , <i>Lodderomyces</i> , <i>Metschnikowia</i> , <i>Pichia</i> , <i>Schizosaccharomyces</i> , <i>Saccharomycodes</i> , <i>Zygosaccharomyces</i> , <i>Alternaria alternata</i> , <i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i> , <i>Aspergillus niger</i> , <i>Aspergillus ochraceus</i> , <i>Aspergillus ustus</i> , <i>Macrophomina phaseolina</i> and <i>Penicillium citrii</i>	378-382
<i>Marrubium vulgare</i>	essential oil	<i>Penicillium digitatum</i> , <i>Botrytis cinerea</i> , <i>Fusarium solani</i> and <i>Aspergillus niger</i>	383-385
<i>Matricaria chamomilla</i>	crude chamomile oil, farnesene, (-) - α -bisabolol and bisabololoxides	<i>Trichophyton mentagrophytes</i>	386-387
<i>Medicago sativa</i>	saponin-rich fractions	<i>Candida albicans</i>	388-389
<i>Melilotus officinalis</i>	crude extracts were evaluated against	<i>Candida inconspicua</i> , <i>C. guilliermondii</i> , <i>C. albicans</i> , <i>C. krusei</i> , <i>C. lusitaniae</i> , <i>C. glabrata</i> , <i>C. parapsilosis</i> , <i>C. methapsilosis</i> , <i>C. ortopsilosis</i> , <i>Microsporum canis</i> , <i>Trichophyton mentagrophytes</i> var. <i>interdigitale</i> , <i>Trichophyton mentagrophytes</i> var. <i>mentagrophytes</i> , <i>Trichophyton rubrum</i> and <i>Tricophyton violaceum</i>	390-393
<i>Mirabilis jalapa</i>	acetone, chloroform, ethanol and methanol extracts of the leaves	<i>Aspergillus flavus</i> , <i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i> , <i>Aspergillus niger</i> and <i>Aspergillus terreus</i>	394-395
<i>Morus alba</i>	ethyl acetate twig extracts	<i>Trichophyton rubrum</i>	396-397
<i>Narcissus tazetta</i>	ethanolic extract	<i>Nigrospora oryzae</i> , <i>Microsporum canis</i> , <i>Pleuralus ostreatus</i> , <i>Curvularia lunata</i> , <i>Trichophyton longifusus</i> , <i>Drechsleza rostrata</i> , <i>Aspergillus niger</i> , <i>candida albicans</i> , and <i>Alefcheria boydii</i>	398-399
<i>Nasturtium officinale</i>	oil	<i>Candida albicans</i>	400-401
<i>Nerium oleander</i>	crude extracts	<i>Aspergillus niger</i> , <i>Aspergillus flavus</i> , <i>Aspergillus fumigates</i> , <i>Fusarium moniliforme</i> , <i>Penicillium expansum</i> and <i>Rhizopus oryzae</i>	402-404
<i>Nicotiana tabacum</i>	methanol and water extracts of the leaf and ground snuff	<i>Candida albicans</i> and <i>Malassezia furfur</i>	405-407
<i>Ononis spinosa</i>	root aqueous extract, butanol extract and ash	<i>Candida albicans</i> , <i>Candida glabrata</i> , <i>Candida tropicalis</i> , <i>Candida krusei</i> , <i>Candida guilliermondii</i> ,	408-411

		<i>Candida parapsilosis</i> , <i>Candida pelliculosa</i> , <i>T. rubrum</i> <i>E. floccosum</i> and <i>M. gypseum</i>	
<i>Phoenix dacylifera</i>	water, acetone and methanol extracts of leaves and pits	<i>Fusarium oxysporum</i> , <i>Fusarium sp.</i> , <i>Fusarium solani</i> , <i>Aspergillus flavus</i> , <i>Alternaria alternata</i> , <i>Alternaria sp.</i> and <i>Trichoderma sp.</i>	412-413
<i>Reseda lutea</i>	methanolic leaves and flower extracts	<i>Candida albicans</i>	414-415

2. Conclusion

The resistance of pathogenic fungi to antifungal drugs is one of the major public health problem. Plant extracts have shown inhibitory effect on the growth of wide range of fungi. They are represented a good alternative for prevention and treatment of fungal diseases. The current review highlighted the antifungal effects of medicinal plants.

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